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Fiber/matrix interface : a key component in a self reinforced polypropylene composite

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Context

Willing to process composite materials by thermoforming

- Glass mat reinforced polypropylene (GMT PP)
- Self reinforced polypropylene (SRP)

THERMOFORMING

Interface evolution due to flowing, deformation, and cooling of the multilayer composite

PRE-CONSOLIDATION (MULTILAYERS)

Hot calendaring
“Intra”layer **interfaces** evolution
Interlayer **interface** creation

Fiber-matrix interface is at stake during each step of the process, and is known to be a key parameter to ensure the best stress transfer from matrix to reinforcing fibers → understanding and characterization are required to design the most relevant interface for a composite

SEMI-FINISHED PRODUCT (1 LAYER)

Dry impregnation

Fiber-matrix **interface** created after running through the calender (heat + pressure)

SUMMARY

- ❑ Context and methodology
- ❑ Interface creation
 - ❑ Wetting
 - ❑ Interdiffusion
 - ❑ Crystallisation
- ❑ Interface characterization
 - ❑ Mechanical
 - ❑ Morphological
- ❑ Conclusions and perspectives

Fiber-matrix interface is a particular 3D-zone (interphase) that can be considered at different structural levels : molecular (physical and chemical interactions), microscopic (single fiber and matrix), macroscopic (whole composite).

Several phenomena during construction

Mechanical characterization

Morphological observation

Temperature process window

Wetting and adhesion effect

- Fibers surface energy
 - Indirect method by single fiber contact angle measurement (*calculation via Owens-Wendt-Rabel-Kaelble*)
- Wettability of molten matrix
 - At process temperature
 - Indirect result by measuring the contact angle of a molten matrix droplet onto known substrates

Adhesion effect

$$W_A = 2\sqrt{(\gamma_s^D \gamma_l^D)} + 2\sqrt{(\gamma_s^{ND} \gamma_l^{ND})}$$

Model system : PP/glass with compatible sizing **VS** PP/glass washed **VS** PP/glass burned

Studied system : PP/PP with sizing **VS** PP/PP washed

Interdiffusion

- Rheology gives access to multiple characteristic times : macromolecules relaxation times thanks to time-temperature-transformation (TTT) giving master curves

→ Determination and extrapolation of the relaxation times

τ_n : average time in number, corresponding to the shortest chains

τ_w : average time in weight, corresponding to the longest chains

$\tau_{max \eta''}$: maximum of chains moving

$\tau_{carreau}$: average time in mass, taking into account long chains, not the number of chains

$$T_g - 50K < T < T_g + 100K \\ \rightarrow \text{WLF}$$

$$\log \tau_T = \frac{-C_1^0(T - T_0)}{C_2^0 + (T - T_0)}$$

$$T > T_g + 50K \\ \rightarrow \text{Arrhenius}$$

$$\log \tau_T = \frac{E_a(T_0)}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right)$$

Interdiffusion

- Rheology gives access to multiple characteristic times : macromolecules relaxation times thanks to time-temperature-transformation (TTT) giving master curves

→ *Determination and extrapolation of the relaxation times*

- According to literature :

$$n = \int_{t_f}^{t_s} \frac{dt}{t_r(T(t))}$$

$n > 1$ leads to a good interface

→ *Temperature process window*

$T_g - 50K < T < T_g + 100K$
→ WLF

$$\log \tau_T = \frac{-C_1^0(T - T_0)}{C_2^0 + (T - T_0)}$$

$T > T_g + 50K$
→ Arrhenius

$$\log \tau_T = \frac{E_a(T_0)}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right)$$

Crystallization DSC & POM

- Nucleating effect from PP fibers

	T_c	$T_{c, \text{onset}}$
Matrix alone	108°C	113°C
Matrix with PP fibers	109°C	113°C

- Nucleating effect from glass fibers

Copolymer PP matrix/ glass

	T_c	$T_{c, \text{onset}}$
Matrix alone	108°C	113°C
Matrix with fiberglass	108°C	113°C

Copolymer PP matrix / PP

Homopolymer iPP matrix/ glass

	T_c	$T_{c, \text{onset}}$
iPP alone	109°C	114°C
iPP with fiberglass	115°C	117°C

Temperature process window

- Relaxation times of matrix and fibers chains evaluated
- Crystallization dramatically decreases macromolecular chains mobility

$$n = \int_{t_f}^{t_s} \frac{dt}{t_r(T(t))}$$

Multi-scale study: “from micro to macro”

- Monofilament / matrix “massive block”

PULL-OUT

IFSS
Interfacial Shear Strength

$$\tau = \frac{F_{max}}{2\pi r_f L_e}$$

Fiber radius

Embedded length

- Unidirectional composite

According to literature :
interface is better
characterized by its
shear load transfer

**VALIDITY
CONDITIONS**

$$\frac{\varepsilon_{12}}{\varepsilon_{xx}} \gg \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{\varepsilon_{11}}{\varepsilon_{xx}} \\ \frac{\varepsilon_{22}}{\varepsilon_{xx}} \end{array} \right.$$

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Micromechanical results – PP/fiberglass

Table I Interfacial Strength of E-Glass Fiber/PP Resin Droplets with Various Holding Time at 220°C, Cooled in Air from the Melt to Room Temperature

Holding Time at 220°C	0.5 h	1 h	2 h	4 h
τ_d (MPa) (std. dev.)	10.60 ± 2.27	11.39 ± 2.08	11.30 ± 2.18	11.39 ± 2.28

IFSS decreasing with increasing desizing

Matrix compatible sizing : PPgMA
Soxhlet extraction and IR spectroscopy

Micromechanical results – SRP

- Effect of interdiffusion : time and temperature impact on IFSS

$$IFSS = \frac{F_{max}}{2\pi r_f L_e}$$

IFSS should decrease with L_e increasing

However IFSS stays the same

Thus there is also an increase of F_{max}

L_e also considers here the plastic deformation of the fiber (= fiber really embedded in the matrix length + fiber elongation, knowing that initial imposed L_e is always the same)

→ Better interface quality with longer interdiffusion ?

→ Yet to confirm with even longer times

Decorrelation of
IFSS from L_e

Off-axis tensile tests results - SRP

- Chose of the relevant angle to perform the tests with a maximum shear stress
 - Adequate angles based on the literature: between 11° and 15°

$$\sigma_{12} = 2,1 \pm 0,6 \text{ MPa} \quad (28\%)$$

$$\frac{\epsilon_{12}}{\epsilon_{xx}} \gg \frac{\epsilon_{11}}{\epsilon_{xx}} ; \frac{\epsilon_{22}}{\epsilon_{xx}}$$

Multi-scale correlation

Von Mises criteria (*pure shear plasticization of the matrix*) :

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_y = \sigma_y / \sqrt{3}$$

with σ_y = yield stress

Theoretical limit before plasticization of the matrix, in the case of a pure shear stress

For our copolymer PP matrix :

$$\sigma_y = 31 \text{ MPa} \quad \rightarrow \quad \boldsymbol{\tau}_y \approx \mathbf{18 \text{ MPa}}$$

IFSS and σ_{12} must be inferior to τ_y

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{12} &\approx 2 \text{ MPa} \\ \text{IFSS} &\approx 10 \text{ MPa} \\ \text{Von Mises : } \boldsymbol{\tau}_y &\approx 18 \text{ MPa} \end{aligned}$$

Morphology observation – TEM

Bulk matrix : $\sim \varnothing 5\mu\text{m}$ spherulites

Fibre : no distinct morphology, maybe too small

A different morphology from the bulk matrix one seems to occur in a $1\mu\text{m}$ to $2\mu\text{m}$ thick layer between the fibre and the matrix

Room temperature microtomy with an oscillating knife, slices or block previously stained with RuO_4 vapours

Conclusions and perspectives

- ❑ Considered phenomena at stake during the creation of the interface may be correlated to characterized interfaces
 - ❑ Wetting → adhesion effect between different systems
 - ❑ Interdiffusion → evaluation of the appropriate process duration according to relaxation times
 - ❑ Crystallization → affects macromolecular chains mobility
- ❑ Morphology observation shows an interlayer presence between the fiber and the bulk matrix
- ❑ End of life and recyclability studies on going

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